

FINITE SUMS OF CONSECUTIVE TERMS OF A SECOND ORDER LINEAR RECURRENCE RELATION

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Abstract

Let a , b , p , and q be integers. Let $W_0(a, b; p, q) = a$, $W_1(a, b; p, q) = b$, and for $n \geq 2$, let $W_n(a, b; p, q) = pW_{n-1}(a, b; p, q) + qW_{n-2}(a, b; p, q)$. Let n and m be nonnegative integers. We will find a formula for $\sum_{i=n}^{n+m} W_i(a, b; 1, q)$.

1. Introduction

We begin by defining a Horadam sequence [1].

Definition 1. Let a , b , p , and q be integers. Let $W_0(a, b; p, q) = a$, $W_1(a, b; p, q) = b$, and for $n \geq 2$, let

$$W_n(a, b; p, q) = pW_{n-1}(a, b; p, q) + qW_{n-2}(a, b; p, q).$$

Let $X_n(a, b; p, q) = W_{n+1}(a, b; p, q) + W_{n-1}(a, b; p, q)$ for $n \geq 1$. Let $U_n = W_n(0, 1; p, q)$ and $V_n = X_n(0, 1; p, q)$ for $n \geq 0$. Finally, we define $H_n(a, b) = W_n(a, b; 1, 1)$ for $n \geq 0$.

When there is no confusion regarding the initial values a and b and recurrence coefficients p and q , we write $W_n(a, b; p, q)$ as W_n . Note that the Fibonacci numbers are $F_n = W_n(0, 1; 1, 1)$, the Lucas numbers are $L_n = W_n(2, 1; 1, 1)$, the Pell numbers are $P_n = W_n(0, 1; 2, 1)$, and the Jacobsthal numbers are $J_n = W_n(0, 1; 1, 2)$.

Several authors have studied this topic. Russell [5, 6] did some initial work. Melham [2] showed that for nonnegative integers n and m ,

$$\sum_{i=n}^{n+m} W_i(a, b; p, 1) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{p} V_{(m+1)/2}(a, b; p, 1) (W_{(2n+m+1)/2}(a, b; p, 1) + W_{(2n+m-1)/2}(a, b; p, 1)), & \text{if } m \equiv 1 \pmod{4}; \\ \frac{1}{p} U_{(m+1)/2}(a, b; p, 1) (X_{(2n+m+1)/2}(a, b; p, 1) + X_{(2n+m-1)/2}(a, b; p, 1)), & \text{if } m \equiv 3 \pmod{4}. \end{cases}$$

We will find a formula for

$$\sum_{i=n}^{n+m} W_i(a, b; 1, q)$$

for integers a, b , and q .

To state some of our theorems, we need to define the general r th order linear recurrence, where $r \geq 2$ is an integer.

Definition 2. Let $n \geq 0$ and $r \geq 1$ be integers. Also, let $\{a_i\}_{i=0}^{r-1}$ and $\{c_i\}_{i=1}^r$ be two finite sequences of r integers. The general r th order Horadam sequence is defined by

$$W_n(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{r-1}; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_r) = \begin{cases} a_n, & \text{if } 0 \leq n \leq r - 1; \\ \sum_{i=1}^r c_i W_{n-i}(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{r-1}; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_r), & \text{if } n \geq r. \end{cases}$$

In Section 2, we give a definition and state and prove a helpful lemma. Also, in Section 2, we compute a finite sum of terms involving consecutive U s. Then, in Section 3, we will compute a finite sum of consecutive W s, where a, b , and q are integers and $p = 1$.

2. Finite Sums Involving Consecutive U s

Definition 3. Let $n \geq 0$ and p and q be integers. Let

$$Y_n = W_n(0, q, 2pq; 2p, q - p^2, -pq).$$

Note that when $p = q = 1$, we have $Y_n(0, 1, 2; 2, 0, -1) = F_{n+2} - 1$ [3, A000071]. Also, when $p = 2$ and $q = 1$, $Y_n(0, 1, 4; 4, -3, -2)$ is [3, A094706] and is the convolution of P_n and 2^n . And, when $p = 1$ and $q = 2$, we define $G_n = Y_n(0, 2, 4; 2, 1, -2)$, which is [3, A167030].

Lemma 1. *Let p and q be integers. Then*

$$U_n = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-1-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^i \text{ for } n \geq 0, \tag{1}$$

$$Y_n = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} \text{ for } n \geq 2. \tag{2}$$

We will prove the formula for Y_n . The proof of the formula for U_n is similar and will be omitted.

Proof. The proof is by induction on n .

Base Step. For $n = 2$, the left-hand side of (2) is

$$Y_2 = W_2(0, q, 2pq; 2p, q - p^2, -pq) = 2pq.$$

The right-hand side of (2) is

$$\sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{2-i}{i+1} p^{2-1-2i} q^{i+1} = \binom{2}{1} p^1 q^1 = 2pq.$$

Therefore, the base step is true for $n = 2$.

For $n = 3$, the left-hand side of (2) is

$$Y_3 = W_3(0, q, 2pq; 2p, q - p^2, -pq) = 2p \cdot 2pq + (q - p^2) \cdot q = 4p^2q - q^2 - p^2q = 3p^2q + q^2.$$

The right-hand side of (2) is

$$\sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{3-i}{i+1} p^{3-1-2i} q^{i+1} = \binom{3}{1} p^2 q^1 + \binom{2}{2} p^0 q^2 = 3p^2q + q^2.$$

Therefore, the base step is true for $n = 3$.

For $n = 4$, the left-hand side of (2) is

$$\begin{aligned} Y_4 &= W_4(0, q, 2pq; 2p, q - p^2, -pq) \\ &= 2p \cdot (3p^2q + q^2) + (q - p^2) \cdot 2pq + (-pq) \cdot q \\ &= 6p^3q + 2pq^2 + 2pq^2 - 2p^3q - pq^2 \\ &= 4p^3q + 3pq^2. \end{aligned}$$

The right-hand side of (2) is

$$\sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{4-i}{i+1} p^{4-1-2i} q^{i+1} = \binom{4}{1} p^3 q^1 + \binom{3}{2} p^1 q^2 = 4p^3q + 3pq^2.$$

Therefore, the base step is true for $n = 4$.

Induction Step. Let $n \geq 5$ and assume that the result is true $n - 3$, $n - 2$, and $n - 1$. We will prove the result for n . By the induction hypothesis, we know that

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{n-3} &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-3-i}{i+1} p^{n-4-2i} q^{i+1}, \\ Y_{n-2} &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+1}, \\ Y_{n-1} &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-2-2i} q^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, using the definition of Y_n , we have

$$\begin{aligned} Y_n &= 2pY_{n-1} + (q - p^2)Y_{n-2} - pqY_{n-3} \\ &= 2p \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-2-2i} q^{i+1} + (q - p^2) \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &\quad - pq \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-3-i}{i+1} p^{n-4-2i} q^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Rearranging terms and using the binomial coefficient recurrence relation

$$\binom{a+1}{b} = \binom{a}{b} + \binom{a}{b-1}, \tag{3}$$

twice, we know that for each $i \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} &2 \binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} + \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+2} \\ &\quad - \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} - \binom{n-3-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+2} \\ &= \binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &\quad + \left(\binom{n-1-i}{i+1} - \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} \right) p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &\quad + \left(\binom{n-2-i}{i+1} - \binom{n-3-i}{i+1} \right) p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+2} \\ &= \binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} + \binom{n-2-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &\quad - \binom{n-3-i}{i} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+2}. \end{aligned}$$

Replacing i by $i - 1$ in the last term of this expression, we have

$$\binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} + \binom{n-2-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} + \binom{n-2-i}{i-1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

Combining the last two terms in this expression using (3), we have

$$\binom{n-1-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1} + \binom{n-1-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

Finally, combining the two remaining terms using (3), we have

$$\binom{n-i}{i+1} p^{n-1-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

Summing this last expression for all $i \geq 0$ gives us is what we wanted to prove. Therefore, the induction step is true. This completes the proof by induction. \square

We can arrange the terms of the polynomials U_n and Y_n in the following table. The sums of the rows of the table add up to U_n . We will show that the terms of Y_n appear in the table.

n	Sum						
0	0						
1	1						
2	$1p$						
3	$1p^2$	$1q$					
4	$1p^3$	$2pq$					
5	$1p^4$	$3p^2q$	$1q^2$				
6	$1p^5$	$4p^3q$	$3pq^2$				
7	$1p^6$	$5p^4q$	$6p^2q^2$	$1q^3$			
8	$1p^7$	$6p^5q$	$10p^3q^2$	$4pq^3$			
9	$1p^8$	$7p^6q$	$15p^4q^2$	$10p^2q^3$	$1q^4$		
10	$1p^9$	$8p^7q$	$21p^5q^2$	$20p^3q^3$	$5pq^4$		
11	$1p^{10}$	$9p^8q$	$28p^6q^2$	$35p^4q^3$	$15p^2q^4$	$1q^5$	
12	$1p^{11}$	$10p^9q$	$36p^7q^2$	$56p^5q^3$	$35p^3q^4$	$6pq^5$	
13	$1p^{12}$	$11p^{10}q$	$45p^8q^2$	$84p^6q^3$	$70p^4q^4$	$21p^2q^5$	$1q^6$
14	$1p^{13}$	$12p^{11}q$	$55p^9q^2$	$120p^7q^3$	$126p^5q^4$	$56p^3q^5$	$7pq^6$

Now, we have a corollary to Lemma 1.

Corollary 1. *Let $n \geq 4$. Then*

$$U_n = p^{n-1} + Y_{n-2}.$$

Proof. Let $n \geq 4$, p , and q be integers. By Lemma 1,

$$U_n = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-1-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^i,$$

$$Y_{n-2} = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} U_n &= p^{n-1} + \sum_{i \geq 1} \binom{n-1-i}{i} p^{n-1-2i} q^i \\ &= p^{n-1} + \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{n-2-i}{i+1} p^{n-3-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &= p^{n-1} + Y_{n-2}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Lemma 2. *Let n and m be nonnegative integers. Then*

$$W_n(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) = qU_{n+m+1}. \tag{4}$$

Proof. We fix m and prove the lemma by induction on n . Note that by Lemma 1,

$$\begin{aligned} Y_m &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m-i}{i+1} p^{m-1-2i} q^{i+1}, \\ Y_{m+1} &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i+1} p^{m-2i} q^{i+1}, \\ Y_{m+2} &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+2-i}{i+1} p^{m+1-2i} q^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Base Step. For $n = 0$, the left-hand side of (4) is

$$\begin{aligned} W_0(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_0(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) &= Y_{m+1} - pY_m \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i+1} p^{m-2i} q^{i+1} - p \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m-i}{i+1} p^{m-1-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \left(\binom{m+1-i}{i+1} - \binom{m-i}{i+1} \right) p^{m-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m-i}{i} p^{m-2i} q^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

The right-hand side of (4) is

$$qU_{0+m+1} = qU_{m+1} = q \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m-i}{i} p^{m-2i} q^i = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m-i}{i} p^{m-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

So the left-hand side and right-hand side are equal for $n = 0$.

For $n = 1$, the left-hand side of (4) is

$$\begin{aligned} W_1(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_1(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) &= Y_{m+2} - pY_{m+1} \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+2-i}{i+1} p^{m+1-2i} q^{i+1} - p \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i+1} p^{m-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \left(\binom{m+2-i}{i+1} - \binom{m+1-i}{i+1} \right) p^{m+1-2i} q^{i+1} \\ &= \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i} p^{m+1-2i} q^{i+1}. \end{aligned}$$

The right-hand side of (4) is

$$qU_{1+m+1} = qU_{m+2} = q \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i} p^{m+1-2i} q^i = \sum_{i \geq 0} \binom{m+1-i}{i} p^{m+1-2i} q^{i+1}.$$

So the left-hand side and right-hand side are equal for $n = 1$. Therefore, the base step is true.

Induction Step. Let $n \geq 2$ and assume that the result is true $n - 2$ and $n - 1$. We will prove the result for n .

By the induction hypothesis, we know that

$$\begin{aligned} W_{n-2}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_{n-2}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) &= qU_{n-2+m+1} \\ W_{n-1}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) &= qU_{n-1+m+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, using the recurrence relation for W_n and the induction hypothesis, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &W_n(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) \\ &= qW_{n-2}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) + pW_{n-1}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) \\ &\quad - p((qW_{n-2}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) + pW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q)) \\ &= q(W_{n-2}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_{n-2}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q)) \\ &\quad + p(W_{n-1}(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q) - pW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q)) \\ &= q^2U_{n-2+m+1} + pqU_{n-1+m+1} \\ &= q(qU_{n-2+m+1} + pU_{n-1+m+1}) \\ &= qU_{n+m+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the induction step is true. Therefore, by mathematical induction, the result is true for all integers $n \geq 0$. □

Theorem 1. *Let n and m be nonnegative integers. Then*

$$q \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} U_i = W_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q). \tag{5}$$

Proof. We fix n and prove the result by induction on m .

Base Step. For $m = 0$, the left-hand side of (5) is

$$q \sum_{i=n}^{n+0} p^{n+0-i} U_i = qp^0 U_n = qU_n.$$

The right-hand side of (5) is

$$W_n(Y_0, Y_{0+1}; p, q) = W_n(Y_0, Y_1; p, q) = W_n(0, q; p, q) = qW_n(0, 1; p, q) = qU_n.$$

The left-hand side is equal to the right-hand side so the base step is true.

Induction Step. We assume the result is true for some $m \geq 0$. We will prove the result is true for $m + 1$. Using the induction hypothesis and Lemma 2 we have

$$\begin{aligned} q \sum_{i=n}^{n+m+1} p^{n+m+1-i} U_i &= pq \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} U_i + qU_{n+m+1} \\ &= pW_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) + qU_{n+m+1} \\ &= W_n(Y_{m+1}, Y_{m+2}; p, q). \end{aligned}$$

This is what we wanted to prove. Therefore, by mathematical induction, the result is true. □

Here is a special case of Theorem 1.

Corollary 2. *Let n and m be nonnegative integers. Then*

$$\sum_{i=n}^{n+m} F_i = H_n(F_{m+2} - 1, F_{m+3} - 1).$$

3. Finite Sums of Consecutive $W(a, b; 1, q)$ s

We are now ready to state and prove our main result.

Theorem 2. *Let n and m be nonnegative integers. Then*

$$q \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} W_i = bW_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) + qaW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q).$$

Proof. From an identity in Horadam [1] and Rabinowitz [4], we have

$$W_i = bU_i + qaU_{i-1}.$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} q \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} W_i &= q \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} (bU_i + qaU_{i-1}) \\ &= qb \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} U_i + q^2a \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} U_{i-1} \\ &= bq \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} p^{n+m-i} U_i + qaq \sum_{i=n-1}^{n-1+m} p^{n-1+m-i} U_i \\ &= bW_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q) + qaW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; p, q). \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

When $p = 1$, we have the following corollary.

Corollary 3. *Let $a, b, q, n \geq 0$, and $m \geq 0$ be integers. Then*

$$\sum_{i=n}^{n+m} W_i(a, b; 1, q) = \frac{b}{q} W_n(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; 1, q) + aW_{n-1}(Y_m, Y_{m+1}; 1, q).$$

In addition, we have three special cases of Corollary 3.

Corollary 4. *Let n and m be nonnegative integers. Then*

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} L_i &= H_n(F_{m+2} - 1, F_{m+3} - 1) + 2H_{n-1}(F_{m+2} - 1, F_{m+3} - 1), \\ \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} J_i &= \frac{1}{2} W_n(G_m, G_{m+1}; 1, 2), \\ \sum_{i=n}^{n+m} H_i(a, b) &= bH_n(F_{m+2} - 1, F_{m+3} - 1) + aH_{n-1}(F_{m+2} - 1, F_{m+3} - 1). \end{aligned}$$

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